

"To Study the Motivation Ability of Teacher and Its Effect on Teacher Training Colleges".

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Abstract:- This Research paper explores the motivation ability of Teacher and its effect on teacher training colleges. The ability of Teacher depends on education qualification, experience and training. and its improvement is very important for the teacher educators and training college development. Throughout the world, T.T.C. has acquired an system for the improvement in the quality and facility of T.T.C.. The effective organizations do not come about magically. They are the result of careful communication, planning and strategic decision- making. In teacher training institution human resources are very important to develop competencies, communication and performance skills for the teaching of integrated education, science and technology religions, life skills and healthy and productive living at the T.T.C.

Keywords:- Teacher Motivation Ability, Decision Making, Teacher Training Colleges (T.T.C), Human Resources, Experience, Teacher Educator.

I. INTRODUCTION

Administration and objective of teacher training in a community and its educational objectives. Hence in a democracy, educational institutions must be organized from the democratic point of view. This implies that the administration of T.T.C. should be done in such a way as helps in the realization of the aims for which the T.T.C. exists. Every T.T.C. has certain aims and ideals before it and for the speedy and successful achievement of these ideals before it and for the speedy and successful achievement of these ideals, an efficient administrative and as such it must have a well organized administrative system. Factors essential for an efficient of T.T.C. administration. The Basic purpose of T.T.C. is to facilitate teacher training and teaching- learning. An efficient system of T.T.C. administration enables the right students teacher to receive the right teacher training from the T.T.C. in healthy environment. It means efficient working of the T.T.C. in the field of teacher training goals. Without a well organized system of T.T.C. employee and heads there is bound to be chaos and confusion in the service of the T.T.C.

- Planning
- Proper Staffing
- Effective direction and control
- systematic coordination
- Financing and budgeting
- Effective use of T.T.C. Building
- Target fixing
- Periodical checking and evaluation

- Flexibility
- Appointments as per law
- Campus control committee
- Students Grievances committee
- Teachers grievances committee
- Non teaching staff grievances committee
- Public relations committee
- Central purchase committee
- Library committee
- University diary committee
- Students Accommodation committee
- Computer and sophisticated instruments committee

Superior accomplishment in any field of human behavior is associated with healthy environmental conditions, extraordinary intellect. Motivation ability improve the existing programmes of quality of teacher training. Motivation is, in effect, a means to reduce and manipulate the gap between Teachers and employee in the training Colleges. It is inducing others in a specific way towards goals specifically stated by the motivator. Naturally, these goals as also the motivation system must conform to the corporate policy of the teacher training Colleges. The motivational system must be tailored to the situation and to the organization. Ability in turn depends on education, experience and training and its improvement is a slow and long process. Teachers has to have an aim or goal in T.T.C. It has a personal frame of reference. The goal an individual sets for oneself should be attainable and meaningful. Upon attaining such a goal one tend to experience fulfillment and satisfaction. Naturally heads motivation in the chosen vocation must be a high order.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study and compare the teacher training employee and Teachers level of communication in working.
- To study the role of Teachers and employee in teacher training College.
- To study the relationship of teacher training college To study desired participation their job satisfaction
- To study the various duties of Teachers in teacher training college.

III. RESEARCH METHOD AND PROCEDURE

The T.T.C. of Amravati district was taken for data collection and qualitative analysis. This study included T.T.C. Teachers and employee field survey method to collect data relevant to participation of T.T.C. of Amravati district. The survey tools utilized in this study provide the necessary information to examine the motivation ability of Teachers. In this paper questionnaire tool were used to collect data. There are 100 Teachers and employee field survey method to collect data relevant to participation of T.T.C. of Amravati district.

IV. SAMPLE SELECTION

The population from the purpose of this study was defined as all the permanent faculty members of T.T.C. of Amravati district. The Teachers and employee T.T.C. who have minimum two years experience including their probation period were considered permanent and included in the population of present study.

V. CONCLUSION

This is the picture of the T.T.C. as visualized by the research paper. We realize that all T.T.C. may not be able to work up to it immediately. But it is not an impossible or unduly idealized picture and it does point the correct direction of advance. If the educational authorities and the teachers accept this conception of the T.T.C., we are of the opinion that in spite of the many difficulties and handicaps that exist, it will be possible to bring about many welcome improvements in our Teacher Training Colleges. The Teachers T.T.C. in order to enjoy the respect of his colleagues, should be a man of high profile. The Teachers of T.T.C. acquire knowledge in all faculty, remain in touch with the latest scientific development, professional knowledge, modern methods of teaching, modern movements in education. In addition as to the above the T.T.C. Teachers must have certain general qualities. 1. Lofty sense of duty 2. Broad sympathy 3. Sound Judgment 4. Power of insight into character 5. Love for his work 6. Originality 7. Self control 8. Organising Power 9. Firmness 10. Persuasive Powers of speech 11. General purity of character.

VI. SUGGESTION

Planning should be done with the active co-operation of the staff, the student, teacher and the T.T.C. calendar should be carefully prepared. T.T.C. heads to allot classes to different teacher educators according to their capacity to work and qualifications and division of co-curricular work among them in such a way as to place the right type of teacher educators at their right places. Taking care of the welfare of pupils both inside and outside the classroom including their boarding establishment Supervision and building equipment, registers and accounts. The Teachers of T.T.C. have a sound philosophy of education and be clear about the objectives of education and be prepared to revise and reexamine in the light of changing needs of society.

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